

BO‘LAJAK O‘QITUVCHILARNING KASBIY MADANIYATINI SHAKILLANTIRISH JARAYONI

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In this article, the relevance and theoretical foundations of the problem of developing the professional culture of teachers, the process of developing the professional culture of school teachers, self-control, self-esteem, reflective and creative thinking, value-epistemological and activity-creative analysis. the content of structures and components is highlighted. The article also shows the psychological and pedagogical features and components of the development of the professional culture of teachers.

Key words: professional culture, professional activity, reflection, self-control, self-assessment, psychological, pedagogical.

Introduction. In world pedagogical practice, great attention is paid to ensuring the adaptability of specialists to the requirements of the changing labor market by developing their professional culture and social competence. This trend has recently led to an increase in scientific research by the international scientific community on the problem of "pedagogical worldview". Indeed, the constant growth and change of the political, social and cultural nature of society requires modern specialists, in particular teachers, to have their own professional values and personal beliefs, to be able to accept not only their own, but also other cultures, and to constantly improve their pedagogical worldview and abilities in accordance with social needs. In our country, the main strategic tasks are to improve the quality of training highly qualified personnel for the modernization of the socio-economic sphere, to develop human capital based on the requirements of the labor market, to introduce digital technologies and modern teaching methods into the educational process, to train highly qualified, "creatively thinking, able to make independent decisions, to create the necessary conditions for their manifestation of intellectual abilities and formation as spiritually mature individuals" based on international standards. This requires improving the mechanisms that serve to improve the quality of training of specialists with higher education[1]. It should also be noted that the development of modern education systems and globalization processes are increasing the demand for improving the quality of education. Teachers, as the main actors of the educational process, play an important role in educating students and managing their learning process through their

professional culture. The professional culture of teachers includes not only their pedagogical knowledge and skills, but also their adaptability to social, ethnic and cultural contexts.

Today, the importance of the institutional approach in the educational process is increasing. This approach includes educational institutions and their internal structures, relationships between teachers and students, as well as strategies aimed at increasing the effectiveness of the education system. The process of forming the professional culture of teachers in educational institutions, when implemented through an institutional approach, allows ensuring the professional development of teachers and making their pedagogical activities more effective. At the same time, the process of forming the professional culture of teachers in modern educational conditions depends on many factors. These include the level of training of teachers, their practical experience, strategic directions of the educational institution and socio-economic conditions. Therefore, this article analyzes the process of forming the professional culture of teachers based on the institutional approach and justifies its relevance. As a result, this study serves to further reveal the importance of the process of forming the professional culture of teachers and to develop new approaches aimed at ensuring quality teaching in the education system. The formation of a professional culture of teachers contributes not only to their personal development, but also to increasing the effectiveness of the entire education system. This, in turn, has a positive impact on the future development of society.

Literature review. Uzbek researchers J.D. Alimov studies the process of training teachers through the use of innovative approaches in the education system[2]. M.M. Shodmonova provides an analysis of professional culture and its role in the educational process[13]. E. Khamroev studies the formation of the process of training teachers through modern pedagogical approaches. Seymur Novruzov studies the methods of developing and training teachers' professional culture in the modern education system. He emphasizes the importance of improving the skills of teachers in the process of training based on an institutional approach. D. Kadyrova studies the importance of using pedagogical innovations in the formation of professional culture. She is developing new methodologies for improving the skills of teachers in this area. J. Khamrova studies the role of modern pedagogical technologies in developing the professional culture of teachers. His works consider the professional practices of teachers, ethics and ways of forming professional culture in communication in the educational process.

The process of forming professional culture of teachers in the modern education system has been studied by many researchers. For example, one of the researchers studying

the professional culture of teachers is Elliot Eisner, who focused on the development of pedagogical approaches of teachers through the use of art and aesthetics in education[4]. Eisner emphasizes in his works the importance of a creative approach in forming professional culture of teachers.

Research methodology. The concept of “professional culture” has been defined in many ways in the scientific literature. Professional culture is a certain worldview and special knowledge, qualities, abilities, skills, feelings, value orientations of a person, which are manifested in his subject-labor activity and ensure high efficiency. That is, professional culture is understood as a type of culture associated with the individual characteristics of a person in relation to any type of work[8].

The professional culture of a person is the basis for systematizing the important professional qualities of a specialist, creating ideal professional models of a person, and is of great theoretical and practical importance for the culture of labor and professional activity. Theory and practice are the phenomena of professional culture, which characterize the level of personal qualities of a future specialist as a system of knowledge, skills and qualifications.

L.S. Vygotsky's theory of social constructivism emphasizes the role of the teacher in the educational process and his interaction with the student. He shows the importance of the social environment in the formation of the teacher's professional culture.

L.S. Shulman introduced the concept of "pedagogical content knowledge" in the formation of teachers' professional culture, combining professional knowledge and pedagogical knowledge.

L. Darling-Hammond conducted research on the training of teachers and their professional development[3]. Her work focuses on practical experiences and cooperation in the formation of teachers' professional culture. Linda Darling-Hammond indicates the necessary conditions for the professional development of teachers. She emphasizes that continuing education and training programs play an important role in the formation of teachers' professional culture. In her opinion, the combination of practical experiences and theoretical knowledge is important in the process of teacher training.

The formation of teachers' professional culture is one of the important aspects of the education system. This process is necessary not only to improve the professional skills of teachers, but also to improve the quality of education and provide students with quality knowledge. The institutional approach is of great importance in solving this problem. Let's look at how this process is being implemented using the example of foreign countries and Uzbekistan.

Rivojlangan mamlakatlarning top eytinglardan joy olgan oliy ta'lim muassasalarida ham o'qituvchilarning kasbiy madaniyatini shakllantirish bo'yicha bir qator aniq ishlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Masalan, Garvard Universiteti o'qituvchilar uchun doimiy professional rivojlanish dasturlarini taklif etadi. Bu dasturlar seminarlar, treninglar va master-klasslardan iborat bo'lib, o'qituvchilar pedagogik metodologiyalarni yangilash va o'z bilimlarini oshirish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladilar. O'qituvchilarning kasbiy madaniyatini baholash uchun maxsus tizimlar mavjud. Bu tizimlar o'qituvchilarning dars berish sifatini va o'qituvchilar bilan muloqotini baholashga yordam beradi.

Kembrij Universiteti o'qituvchilarga pedagogik ko'nikmalarni oshirish uchun turli kurslar va sertifikatlar taklif qiladi. O'qituvchilar ushbu kurslarda qatnashib, kasbiy madaniyatlarini rivojlantirish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladilar. O'qituvchilar ilmiy tadqiqotlar olib borish va ta'lim jarayonida innovatsion yondashuvlarni amalga oshirish imkoniyatiga ega.

Yaponiyadagi Mitsubishi Gakuin universitetida xalqaro hamkorlik orqali o'qituvchilar tajribalarini almashish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladi. Xalqaro konferentsiyalar va seminarlar tashkil etiladi. O'qituvchilarga ijtimoiy mas'uliyatni oshirishga qaratilgan dasturlar ishlab chiqilgan. Bu dasturlar orqali o'qituvchilar jamiyatda ijobiy o'zgarishlarga hissa qo'shadilar.

Rivojlangan mamlakatlarning oliy ta'lim muassasalarida o'qituvchilarning kasbiy madaniyatini shakllantirish bo'yicha ko'plab innovatsion yondashuvlar va dasturlar mavjud. Bu jarayonlar orqali o'qituvchilarning professional ko'nikmalari oshiriladi, ta'lim sifatini yaxshilashga erishiladi va jamiyatda ijobiy o'zgarishlar yuzaga keladi.

Tahlil va natijalar. Yuqorida o'rgangan barcha mualliflarning ilmiy izlanishlari va adabiyotlar tahlili natijasida quyidagi xulosalarga kelish mumkin:

1. O'qituvchilarning kasbiy madaniyati: O'qituvchilarning kasbiy madaniyati ularning pedagogik yondoshuvlariga, ijodkorliklariga va amaliy tajribalariga bog'liqdir. O'qituvchilar o'z kasbiy madaniyatlarini shakllantirishda ijodiy va innovatsion yondashuvlarni qo'llashlari zarur.
2. Instituttsional yondashuv: O'qituvchilarning kasbiy madaniyatini shakllantirishda institutlararo hamkorlik va tajriba almashish muhim rol o'ynaydi. Ta'lim tizimidagi o'zgarishlarni muvaffaqiyatli amalga oshirish uchun tashkilotlararo aloqalar mustahkam bo'lishi lozim.
3. Professional rivojlanish: O'qituvchilarni tayyorlash jarayonida doimiy ta'lim va amaliy tajribalar muhimdir. O'qituvchilar uchun professional rivojlanish dasturlari, ularning kasbiy madaniyatini shakllantirishda muhim omil hisoblanadi.

4. Ijtimoiy kontekst: O'qituvchilar jamiyatdagi ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy jarayonlardan xabardor bo'lishlari zarur. Ularning pedagogik faoliyatlari ijtimoiy kontekstga mos ravishda olib borilishi kerak.

Ushbu natijalar zamonaviy ta'lim sharoitida institutsional yondashuv asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning kasbiy madaniyatini shakllantirish jarayonining samaradorligini oshirishga yordam beradi va kelgusida bu sohada yangi tadqiqotlar olib borish uchun asos yaratadi.

Institutsional yondashuv asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning kasbiy madaniyatini shakllantirishning texnologik tizimi ta'lim jarayonini yanada samarali va innovatsion tarzda tashkil etishga yordam beradi. Ushbu tizimning asosiy komponentlari o'qituvchilarni tayyorlash, amaliyot o'tkazish, baholash va monitoring qilishni o'z ichiga oladi. Natijada, bu tizim bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning kasbiy madaniyatini rivojlantirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'ladi.

Xulosa va takliflar. Ushbu ilmiy maqolada zamonaviy ta'lim sharoitida institutsional yondashuv asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning kasbiy madaniyatini shakllantirish jarayoni tahlil qilindi. O'qituvchilarning kasbiy madaniyati ta'lim jarayonining muvaffaqiyatli amalga oshirilishi uchun muhim omil hisoblanadi. Maqolada ko'rsatilganidek, o'qituvchilarning kasbiy madaniyatini shakllantirishda ijodkorlik, innovatsion yondashuvlar, doimiy professional rivojlanish va ijtimoiy kontekstga moslashuv zarurligi ta'kidlandi. Institutsional yondashuv esa o'qituvchilarning o'zaro hamkorlik va tajriba almashish orqali o'z kasbiy madaniyatlarini rivojlantirishlariga imkon yaratadi. Shuningdek, o'qituvchilarning kasbiy madaniyatini shakllantirish jarayonida ta'lim tizimining struktura va funksiyalarining ahamiyati ko'rsatildi. O'qituvchilarni tayyorlash jarayonida amaliy tajribalar va nazariy bilimlarning uyg'unligi, shuningdek, ijtimoiy va madaniy kontekstning ahamiyati muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Adabiyotlar:

1. Shomurodov O. N. Perception and depiction of basic color relationships in painting performance //World Bulletin of Social Sciences. – 2021. – T. 4. – №. 11. – С. 62-65.
2. Shomurodov O. N. HAYKALTAROSHLIK TASVIRIY SAN'ATNING TURI SIFATIDA //Inter education & global study. – 2023. – №. 2. – С. 51-57.
3. Шомуродов О. Н., Авезов Ш. Н. Компьютерные технологии обучения //Вестник науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 21-2 (99). – С. 51-54.
4. Ширинов А. Л., Батиров Д. С., Шомуродов О. Н. Важность цветоведения в изобразительном искусстве //Наука и образование сегодня. – 2021. – №. 5 (64). –

C. 83-85.

5. Sobirova, S. U. (2021, October). A Brief History of the Science of Perspective. In "ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM (pp. 64-67).

6. Sobirova, S. U. (2022). Use of Ready-Made Handouts and Didactic Materials in Drawing Teaching. Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity, 4, 111-116.

7. Olimov S. S., Mamurova D. I. Information Technology in Education //Pioneer: Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 17-22.

8. Olimov S. S., Mamurova D. I. Opportunities to use information technology to increase the effectiveness of education //International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education (INT-JECSE). – 2022. – Т. 14. – №. 02.

9. Ширинов А. Л., Батиров Д. С., Шомуродов О. Н. Важность цветоведения в изобразительном искусстве //Наука и образование сегодня. – 2021. – №. 5 (64). – С. 83-85.

10. Botirov, J. S., Bakaev, S. S., Avliyakov, M. M., Shirinov, A. L., & Abdullaev, S. S. (2021). The same goes for art classes in private schools specific properties. Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government Vol, 27(2).

11. Muzafarovna A. N., Jurayevich J. Q. The role of islam in folk decorative art of Bukhara //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR). – 2020. – Т. 9. – №. 5. – С. 347-350.

12. Muzafarovna A. N. THE ROLE OF ARTISTIC CREATIVITY IN THE PREPARATION OF FUTURE FINE ARTS TEACHERS FOR PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY //Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 1.5 Pedagogical sciences.

13. Muzafarovna, A. N. (2023). IMPROVING FUTURE TEACHERS'SKILLS OF DESIGNING AND MODELING FINE ARTS LESSONS. Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Art, 21-24.

14. Ботиров, Д. С., Шомуродов, О. Н., & Ширинов, А. Л. (2021). МЕТОДИКА ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ИСТОРИИ ИЗОБРАЗИТЕЛЬНОГО ИСКУССТВА. European science, (2 (58)), 101-103.

15. Shomurodov, Oibek. "THE IMPORTANCE OF THE CREATIVE EXHIBITION FOR STUDENTS'CREATIVITY." Actual Problems in Higher Education in the Era of Globalization: International Scientific and Practical Conference. 2023.

16. Shomurodov, O. N. (2022). SAN'AT ASARLARINI TUSHUNISH VA TAHLIL QILISHGA O 'RGATISHDA MAKTAB TASVIRIY SAN'ATI. UMUMINSONIY VA MILLIY QADRIYATLAR: TIL, TA'LIM VA MADANIYAT, 1, 61-64.

17. Абдуллаев, Сухроб Сайфуллаевич. "ЭСТЕТИКА ЦВЕТА В ВОСПИТАНИИ ПЛАСТИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ АРХИТЕКТОРА." PEDAGOGS journali 1.1 (2022): 384-386.
18. Абдуллаев С. С. РОЛЬ СРЕДНЕВЕКОВОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ ВОСТОКА В СОЗДАНИИ СЮЖЕТОВ МИНИАТЮРЫ СРЕДНЕЙ АЗИИ //Inter education & global study. – 2023. – №. 2. – С. 100-108.
19. Laue S., Abdullaev S. S. Legends and True Stories about the Samanid Mausoleum //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 308-311.
20. Abdullayev¹ S. F., Abdullayev S. S. TRANSLATION OF CULTURAL VALUES IN THE ARTISTIC HERITAGE OF TRADITIONAL APPLIED ARTS OF BUKHARA.
21. Abdullaev S., Mamatov D. Pedagogical foundations in the teaching of folk arts and crafts of Uzbekistan in the training of teachers of fine arts //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 420. – С. 10019.
22. Умедов, Шахзод, and Нафиса Авлиякулова. "КУЛЬТУРА И ПСИХОЛОГИЯ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОГО ОБЩЕНИЯ." Современная педагогика и психология: проблемы и перспективы. 2020.
23. Азимов, Б. Б., Азимова, М. Б., Тухсанова, В. Р., & Сулаймонова, М. Б. (2021). Педагогические, психологические и методические основы проведения бесед об искусстве. European science, (2 (58)), 38-40.
24. Сулаймонова, М. Б., Азимов, Б. Б., Азимова, М. Б., & Тухсанова, В. Р. (2021). Достижение эстетической и нравственной зрелости обучающихся изобразительному искусству. European science, (3 (59)), 53-56.
25. Sulaymonova, M. B. (2024). ISSUES OF IMPROVING BUKHARA MUSEUMS. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 4(4), 301-304.
26. Sulaymonova, M. B. "TASVIRIY SAN'ATNI O 'QITISHDA NAMKORLIKDAGI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH ASOSLARI." Inter education & global study 5 (2023): 13-19.
27. Mukhiba, Sulaymonova. "The role and importance of fine arts in imparting knowledge and skills to students." International Engineering Journal For Research & Development 5.7 (2020): 3-3.